

E-Commerce and its contribution in reducing the Operating cost of the Business

Dr. Nabaghan Mallick¹, Shalini Jaiswal²

¹(Asst. Prof. of Commerce) Dharanidhar University, Keonjhar
n.mallickfinance@gmail.com Mob-No.9937940035

²(Asst. Prof. in Dept. of Professional Studies) Dharanidhar University, Keonjhar
Email-Id- shalinijaiswal0207@gmail.com Mob. No.- 8847860793

ABSTRACT :

Research has been done to know how the functioning of E-commerce has allowed companies to commence their business processes and reduce their operational cost. This study contains a comparative study of e-commerce and traditional commerce to reveal how e-commerce has contributed in facilitating the business process by providing an online platform for buying and selling of tangible goods and services and thereby facilitating smooth transaction and minimising the operational cost. E-commerce also plays a major role in increasing the abilities of the company to serve their customer's need and to raise their standard of living. The depth of the study is to focus on the recent trends in e-commerce which have a positive or negative impact on its functioning. Thereby investigating the factors that determine the quality in e-commerce to be able to achieve customer satisfaction and reduce the risk of insecurity. Findings the research showed that there is a direct correlation between the use of e-commerce and improve customer service. E-commerce has improved the availability of information, reduce processing errors, reduce response time, lowered cost of services and has effectively raised customer satisfaction level.

Key Words :- E-commerce, Operating Cost, recent trends, reduce response time, standard of living

INTRODUCTION

It is important to understand that as the businesses grow, they faced ever-growing cost for goods and services. E-commerce has provided the new way of doing the business by providing an online platform for buying and selling of good and services and making it easier for businesses to reach customers and sell their products online. In this study, we will know the role of e-commerce in reducing operational costs and how it can help businesses maximise their profits.

E-commerce has become an essential part of the business world. It enables businesses to sell their products and services online, reaching customers from all over the world. However, e-commerce also comes with its own set of costs. Operational costs are the expenses that a business incurs in order to keep its operations running smoothly. These costs can include salaries, rent, utilities, and other expenses that are necessary to keep the business running.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

- Brynjolfsson, E, Hu, Y., & Rahman, M.S. (2013). "Competing in the age of Omnichannel Retailing." MIT Sloan Management review: This paper highlights how the rise of Omnichannel Retailing integrating online and offline channels affect competition and consumer behavior. The researcher argues that Omnichannel strategies enhance customer experience by more convince and seamless interaction across different channels. Companies that effectively implement Omnichannel strategies can gain competitive advantage by superior services and personalized experience, leading to increase customer loyalty and higher sales.
- Chopra, S., & Meindl, P.(2016). " Supply chain management strategy, planning and operations ". Pearson. :- Chopra and Meindl provide a comprehensive overview of supply Chain management, focusing on strategic planning and operational aspects. The book covers key concepts such as supply chain design, forecasting, inventory management and logistics. The author highlights the importance of integrating supply chain activities to enhance efficiency and responsiveness. They also discuss the role of technology in supply chain management, emphasizing on how digital tools and data analysis can optimize supply chain performance and reduce cost.
- Deighton, J.,and kornfeld, L. (2009). "Interactivity's Unanticipated consequences for marketers and marketing." Journal of interactive marketing, 23(1), 4-10 :- Deighton and Kornfeld examine the unexpected efforts of interactive marketing on businesses and consumers. The paper discuss how interactivity through digital channels, change the dynamics of marketing by enabling real time communication and feedback. The author identifies certain consequences such as increased customer empowerment, the need for marketers to be more responsive, and the potential for information overload. They argue that while interactivity offers opportunities for personalized marketing

and improve customer relationship, it also requires marketer to adopt to new challenge and manage the complexity of interactive platform effectively.

- Zhu, K. (2004). " The complimentarily of information technology infrastructure and e-commerce capability. A resource-based assessment of their business value." Journal of management information system 21(1), 1672- 202:- In this paper, Zhu examines the synergistic relationship between information technology infrastructure and e-commerce capabilities assessing their combined impact on business value. Using a resource-based views, the study analysis how robust IT infrastructure enhances the effectiveness of e-commerce initiatives. Zhu argue that the interaction of IT infrastructure with e-commerce capabilities create significant competitive advantages by improving operational efficiency customer service and innovation. The findings suggest that business with well-developed IT infrastructures are better positioned to leverage e-commerce for greater financial performance and market success. The paper underscores the importance of investing on both IT and e-commerce capayto maximize their complimentary benefits.
- Turban, E., Outland, J., king, D., lee, J.K, liang, TP., the turban DC (2018):- " A managerial and social network prospective sringer:- this book provides a comprehensive overview of electronic commerce from both managerial and social network prospective . It covers the fundamental concept of e-commerce, including its business model technological infrastructure and the impact of business operation. The author emphasis the role of social network in shaping e-commerce strategies, discussing how platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn influences consumer behaviour and marketing practices. The book also explores the importance of data analytics, cyber-security, and mobile commerce. BY integrating managerial insights with the dynamics of social networks, the authors offer a holistic view of how e-commerce is transforming businesses and consumer interaction.

Case Studies and Real world examples:-

1. Amazon

Haucap and heimeshoff (2014) explore how Amazon's efficient supply chain management and large-scale operations contribution to its cost leadership strategy. Amazon's extensive use of automation in warehousing and logistics has significantly reduced its operating costs, the company's investment in technology such as robotic and AI has streamlined operations, resulting in cost savings.

2. Alibaba:

Qin and Jiang (2011) discuss how Alibaba's integration of technology in its operations has driven cost reduction and operational efficiencies. Alibaba's e-commerce ecosystem leverages data analytics to optimize inventory and Logistics. The platform's use of big data has enhanced its operational efficiency, reducing cost and improving service.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The outcome of this study will educate businessman and the general public on the role of E-commerce in reducing the operational cost of business organizations.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To examine the role of E-Commerce in reducing operational cost.
- To identify other benefits accruable from E-Commerce.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

- H1 : There is no positive relation between "e-commerce" & cut down of "operational cost".
- H0 : There is a positive relation between "e-commerce" & cut down of "operational cost".

WHAT IS E-COMMERCE ?

E- Commerce refers to a wide range of business activity for product and service. It also pertains to "any form of business transaction in which the parties interact electronically rather than by physical exchange or direct physical contact." Ecommerce is process of conducting any transfer of ownership or rights to use goods and services through a computer mediated network without using any paper document.

Ecommerce refers to paperless exchange of business information using following ways:-

- Electronic data exchange (EDE)
- Electronic mail
- Electronic bulletin boards
- Electronic fund transfer
- Other network-based technologies.

WHAT IS OPERATING COST?

Operational costs are the expenses that a business incurs in order to keep its operations running smoothly. These costs can include salaries, rent, utilities, and other expenses that are necessary to keep the business running. Operating costs include both costs of goods sold (COGS) and other operating expenses—often called selling, general, and administrative (SG&A) expenses. Operating costs are the ongoing expenses incurred from the normal day-to-day of running a business.

Operating costs will also include the cost of goods sold, which are the expenses directly tied to the production of goods and services. Some of the costs include:

- Direct material costs
- Direct labour
- Rent of the plant or production facility
- Benefits and wages for the production workers
- Repair costs of equipment
- Utility costs and taxes of the production facilities.

Impact of E-Commerce on Operational Costs

E-commerce plays a very vital role in reducing the operating cost of the business. Some of the major contribution of E-commerce is that it helps the businesses to operate with minimum overhead cost. Carrying on businesses through E-commerce do not need maintain any physical storefront or warehouse, which in turns reduces the rent, maintenance & repair and utility cost. Moreover, E-commerce businesses can operate with fewer staff, this significantly reduces Labour cost.

Ho E-Commerce Helps to Reduce Costs?

E-commerce can help in reducing the operational cost of businesses in several ways.

i. Reduced Overhead Cost:

E-commerce facilitates the running of the businesses without maintaining any physical storefronts, thereby reducing costs associated with rent, maintenance and repair, utilities etc.

ii. Inventory Management:

E-commerce allows for more efficient inventory management by providing real time tracking of inventory levels through automated systems. This helps in identify the overstocks or stockouts in the business and helps in reducing the cost associated with excess inventory/overstocks or stockouts and the risk of obsolete inventory.

iii. Supply Chain Efficiency:

E-commerce facilitates the direct and streamlined communication among the supplier customers and the business through digital channels. A streamline communication helps in reducing the communication costs associated with various intermediaries and this also helps in the enhancement of overall efficiency.

iv. Automated order fulfilment:

E-commerce provides an electronic platform that helps in automation of several business processes, such as order fulfilment processing, inventory management, and payment processing. This reduces the need for manual labour or staff, thereby reducing the labour cost and minimises the chance of errors in order processing.

v. Customer self-service:

E-commerce allows for the implementation of customer self-service options such as automated order tracking, returns processing and FAQs. This helps in reducing the need for extensive customer service staff and associated costs.

vi. Marketing and Advertising:

E-commerce provides businesses with cost effective digital marketing channels including social media, email campaigns, and search engine optimization. This online marketing reduces the need for expensive traditional advertising methods.

vii. Reduced Paperwork:

E-commerce provides a digital working platform to businesses by facilitating Digital transaction and documentation. This in turns reduces the need for manual paperwork, and down on printing and storage costs.

viii. Global Reach:

E-commerce facilitates the businesses to expand globally or to reach a global audience without any geographical boundaries and without the need for a physical presence in multiple location. This can lead to economies of scale and reduces per unit operational cost.

ix. Efficient Decision Making:

E-commerce provides data that can be analysed to make informed efficient business decision. Data related to understanding customer behaviour, tastes and preference and recent market trends that allows the businesses to take informed decision regarding optimizing their operation, reducing in efficiencies and cost.

x. Reduced physical Infrastructure:

E-commerce eliminates or reduces the need of physical infrastructure due to its automated streamline order processing system. There is no need of traditional brick and mortar stores.

Overall, E-commerce can lead to significant cost savings for businesses by improving efficiency, reducing overhead and optimizing various operational process and operate more efficiently in the competitive e-commerce landscape.

Benefits of E-commerce to businesses

E-commerce offers numerous benefits to businesses including:

1. Global Reach:

E-commerce provides an online platform for reaching a global audience, breaking down the geographical barriers and expanding market reach.

2. 24X7 Availability:

Unlike the physical storefronts e-commerce websites are accessible 24 X 7, allowing customers to shop at their convenience, leading to increased sales opportunities.

3. Reduced Costs:

E-commerce eliminates the need for physical storefronts, reducing rent, maintenance utilities, and labour costs. Its streamline processes like inventory management and automated order fulfilment leading to cost saving.

4. Increases Efficiency:

E-commerce provides an automated process of inventory management order processing and appropriate online method of payment and shipping method as well as facilitated the exchange operation which helps in improving operational efficiency and reduces the likelihood of errors.

5. Full information about the product:

E-commerce helps the businesses to personalise their market by providing full information about the product and customers tastes and preferences. It provides the valuable data which help the businesses to deal with competitors openly and widely.

6. Enhanced Customer Experience:

Due to the systematic and automated reliable process of order processing and appropriate methods of payment as well and shipping provides a seamless and convenient shopping experience to the customers. This helps in creating a positive customer experience which result in increasing the sales.

7. Fast Mover Advantages:

E-commerce helps the businesses in providing relevant data about today's competitive marketplace which allows them to stay ahead of competitors and meet the evolving needs of customers.

8. Wide Range of product offering:

E-commerce allows businesses to expand their product offering without the constraints of physical space, catering to diverse customer preferences, and increasing sales potential.

E-commerce vs Offline business

1. Presence of Intermediaries:

Offline businesses have face to face interaction with the customers allowing for personal connections and immediate assistance which is only possible by the presence of intermediaries and physical presence at multiple location whereas e-commerce eliminates the need of such intermediaries as it does not require any physical interaction with the customer. It relies on digital communication channels such as email, live chat, and social media.

2. Physical Presence:

Offline businesses must have physical storefront, or it must be physically presence in multiple location where customers can visit to make purchase. While e-commerce business operates exclusively online without a physical presence.

3. Expenses:

Carrying an offline business is more expensive as it requires brick and mortar store to be physically presence in the multiple location. It also involves labour cost and maintenance cost. Whereas carrying on businesses through E-commerce is not much expensive as it eliminates such labour cost and other expenses involved expenses in offline business.

4. Accessibility:

Offline business work for a fixed hours it typically has operating hours and require customer to visit in person for making the purchase. E-commerce businesses are 24 X 7 accessible from anywhere with an internet connection allowing customers to shop at their convenience.

5. No Geographical Boundaries:

Offline business cannot reach to wide variety of customer as it is difficult for them to be present in every location. It generally serves a local or regional customer base. Whereas E-commerce businesses does not have any geographical boundaries. It has the potential to reach a global audience, as they are not limited by geographical constraints.

6. Overhead Cost:

Offline business has more overhead cost including rent, utilities, and staffing for physical locations. While e-commerce businesses typically have lower overhead cost since they do not require physical storefronts.

7. Security Concerns:

Carrying on business offline may face security concerns related to physical theft and vandalism. Whereas E-commerce businesses must prioritise cybersecurity measures to protect customer data and prevent online fraud.

CONCLUSION :

These Studies collectively demonstrate the effectiveness of E-commerce to significantly reduce operating costs access various aspect of business operation by considering all the various factors of e-commerce in facilitating trade and conducting the exchange of goods and services from the initial manufacturer to the final consumer such as administration, inventory management, marketing, sales.

It can be clearly concluded that e-commerce is an allrounder and efficient means of reducing a business operating costs which in turn reduces the cost of production and sales of a product. The various role of e-commerce discusses in the research clearly signifies the importance of E-commerce in generating higher profitability of a business, and eliminating the excess of operating cost which is the desirable outcome for every business owner.

REFERENCES :

1. Chopra, S, & Meindl, P. (2016) "Supply chain Management: Strategy, Planning and Operation Pearson
2. Deighton, J., & Kornfeld, L. (2009). "Interactivity's unanticipated consequences for Marketer and Marketing. 23(I), 4-10.
3. Haucap, J., & Heimeshoff, U. (2014). "google, Facebook, Amazon, ebay,: Is the Internet driving completion of market monopolization?" International economics and economic policy, II(1-2), 49-61
4. Rajneesh Shahjee (2015), The Impact of Electronic commerce on Business organisation. Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary studies, ISSN: 2278 – 8808, NOV and DEC 2016. Vol.4/27,
5. Turban. E., Outland, I, King, D., Lee., J.K., Liang, T-P., & Turban D.C.(2018). "Electronic commerce 2018: A managerial and social Network perspective". Springer.
6. Zhu. K. (2004). "The complementarily of Information Technology Infrastructure and E-commerce capability:- A Resource Based Assessment of Their Business Value". Journal of Management Information System, 21(1), 167-202.
7. Zhai CJ (2010), Research on post adoption behaviour of B2B e-market place in China/ Business Administration and Institutional innovation China.
8. M. Bharadwaj & N.Mallick : E-commerce : 2023 : Kalyani Publisher
9. Dr. Sanjeeb Kumar Dey : Introduction to E-commerce : 2023 : VK Publisher
10. Tulasi Ram Kandula & R. Jyosna Reddy : Concept of E-commerce : 2023 : Himalaya Publishing House
11. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/role-e-commerce-reducing-operational-cost-meenakshi-s-wf3sc>
12. https://sist.sathyabama.ac.in/sist_naac/documents/1.3.4/1922-b.com-b.com-batchno-83.pdf
13. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330359333_The_Role_of_E-Commerce_to_Reduce_Costs_and_its_Impact_on_Small_Medium-Sized_Companies